

Appendix

Process Mining Challenges Perceived by Analysts: An Interview Study

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The following material provides additional information to section

3 Research Method

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Interview Protocol

(T): To be asked referring to the process mining task (G): To be asked referring to general work practices

ACTIVITIES, TARGET ARTIFACTS and USE of ARTIFACTS

- Can you briefly summarize the main steps of your analysis today and explain why you worked in this way? (T)
- Would you always follow the same steps in practice? (G)
- What information did you aim to gather during the analysis? Why? (T)
- Would you always focus on gathering the same information in practice or does that change from case to case? (G)
- How did you use the provided artifacts during the analysis? Why were they useful? (T)

GOALS

- Can you summarize the main goals of your analysis today? (T)
- Do you always work with these goals in mind in practice? (G)
- Do you always have clear analysis goals or objectives in practice? (G)
- On a scale from 1 to 10, how much do you think that the analyses you conduct in practice are exploratory? By exploratory we mean that you spend time refining research questions, generating new questions for the analysis.

STRATEGIES, START and TERMINATION CRITERIA

- Did you follow any specific strategy (plan of action to achieve a certain goal) when trying to answer the questions today? (T)
- Did your analysis approach change during the analysis? If so, how? (T)
- Would you follow the same approach in practice, with other event logs? (G)
- How did you decide where to start your analysis from? (T)
- In practice, how do you usually choose where to start your analysis from? (G)
- How did you decide that it was time to stop the analysis? Did you follow any criteria? (T)
- In practice, how do you usually decide that it is time to stop the analysis? (G)

CHALLENGES

- Is there anything that you found challenging during the task today? (T)
- And in general, what do you think are the biggest challenges of process mining? (G)
- On a scale from 1 to 10, how much do you think that good tool knowledge helps to overcome process mining challenges? (G)
- Do you think that combining different process mining tools is an opportunity for the analysis or do you think it is too complicated/not needed? (G)
- Taking a look at process mining, where do you think there is more need for methodological or operational support? (G)

Participants Overview

The table contains the overview of the 41 participants (p) of the study. It highlights the **Sector**, to which the participant's affiliation/company belongs, the participant's job role (**Role**) at the time of the data collection, years of **Experience in Process Mining and Data Science**, the self-rated **Expertise** of the participant in **Process Mining** and **Process Analytics** (ranked on a Likert scale with values "novice", "basic", "average", "good", "advanced"), the number of process mining tools the participant knew and the number of analyzed event logs two years prior to the data collection.

Participant	Sector	Role	Experience		Expertise		# known Tools	# analyzed Eventlogs (in past 2 years)
			in Process Mining (in years)	in Data Science (in years)	Process Mining	Process Analytics		
p1	Enterprise Software	Product Manager	2	Up to 1	Good	Basic	1	1
p2	Academia	PhD Student	1	1-3	Average	Average	3	1
p3	National Laboratory	Senior R&D Staff	3	> 10	Good	Average	2	2-5
p4	Consulting	Senior R&D Staff	2	6-10	Average	Average	3	1
p5	Consumer Goods	Process Analyst	2.5	Up to 1	Average	Average	1	2-5
p6	Freelance	Process Mining Consultant	2	1-3	Good	Good	2	2-5
p7	Academia	Professor	10	6-10	Advanced	Average	3	6-10
p8	Academia	Assistant Professor	10	4-5	Advanced	Good	2	2-5
p9	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	3.5	1-3	Good	Good	2	> 20
p10	Academia	Senior Researcher	1	None	Novice	Novice	1	None
p11	Freelance	Business Analyst	8	> 10	Advanced	Advanced	4	6-10
p12	Academia	Assistant Professor	8	6-10	Advanced	Good	4	2-5
p13	Enterprise Software	Partner Relationships Manager	1	Up to 1	Basic	Basic	1	1
p14	Enterprise Software	Product Manager / Engineer	3	1-3	Good	Good	1	10-20
p15	Academia	Assistant Professor	6	6-10	Good	Average	3	2-5
p16	Academia	PhD Student	4	None	Average	Average	2	2-5
p17	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	4	1-3	Good	Average	1	10-20
p18	Academia	Senior Researcher	7	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	4	6-10
p19	Academia	Assistant Professor	8	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	4	6-10
p20	Enterprise Software	Partner Relationships Manager	0.3	Up to 1	Basic	Basic	1	1
p21	Academia	Graduate Student	3	1-3	Average	Average	4	None
p22	Academia	Graduate Student	0.3	1-3	Basic	Basic	1	1
p23	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	1	Up to 1	Average	Average	2	2-5
p24	Enterprise Software	Analytics Product Manager	3	1-3	Good	Good	1	2-5
p25	Food Processing	Process Analyst	4	> 10	Good	Good	2	2-5
p26	Packaging	Digital Project Manager	7	1-3	Good	Good	1	2-5
p27	Financial	Process Mining Analyst	1	1-3	Average	Average	5	2-5
p28	Academia	Professor	4	> 10	Good	Good	4	2-5
p29	Academia	PhD Student	6	6-10	Good	Average	5	2-5
p30	Academia	Professor	10	1-3	Average	Good	5	2-5
p31	Telecommunications	Business Consultant	2	> 10	Basic	Good	1	2-5
p32	Academia	PhD Student	2	1-3	Average	Basic	2	2-5
p33	Constructions	Operational Excellence Lead	3	4-5	Advanced	Advanced	1	6-10
p34	Government	Consultant	10	> 10	Good	Good	2	6-10
p35	Insurance	Process Analyst	2	Up to 1	Good	Good	1	2-5
p36	Academia	PhD Student	6	1-3	Good	Good	3	2-5
p37	Insurance	Operational Excellence Lead	5	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	1	> 20
p38	Academia	Professor	8	4-5	Good	Good	4	6-10
p39	Academia	Senior Researcher	7	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	5	10-20
p40	Academia	Senior Researcher	16	4-5	Advanced	Advanced	4	> 20
p41	Academia	PhD Student	7	6-10	Good	Advanced	2	2-5

Coding Scheme

The following table contains the final coding scheme. It provides information regarding the project phase (**Phase**) the code is assigned to, it's identifier (**ID**), a description (**Description**) that was used by the authors to identify whether a statement can be assigned to the code, an exemple statement (**Statement**) illustrating the occurrence of the code, the frequency (**Freq.**) in which it occurs in the data, the number of total participants supporting the statement (**No.**) and the number of participants divided by practitioners (**#P**) and academics (**#A**).

Phase	ID	Code	Description The code combines statements related to perceived challenges ...	Statement	Freq.	No.	#P	# A
Defining Research Question	C1	Question Formulation	...due to either performing the project based on an external, prescribed goal , due to working with a loosely defined goal or a lack thereof and covers perceived challenges during the formulation of questions .	I think the analysis should always follow the question. So, I would base my steps on the question, but at the same time, it is very often hard to identify the correct question. (P36)	20	10	6	4
	C2	Access and Use of Process Mining Tools	...due to the unavailability of a process mining tool , due to a missing governance to structure the tool usage in the organization or due to a general low usability which results in avoiding the application of a process mining tool.	I think the biggest challenge is that companies... so most companies I think do not have the tools implemented. (P22)	7	6	3	3
	C3	Process Mining Suitability	...associated with the application and selection of process mining as a suitable method for a task. It covers the application of process mining on the individual level as well as its general application and governance in an organization.	I think it makes a lot of sense to use process mining methods. But at the same time, a lot of the questions you don't need process mining to answer or, you can use process mining as a tool in the toolbox where you have a lot of other tools that you use around. (P12)	6	4	3	1
Data Collection	C4	Data Extraction	...during the retrieval, i.e., identification and extraction, of event data from any kind of source.	I think gathering the data is a technical challenge and there's not much to elaborate there, it's just that quite often you need to extract data from information systems that are not, yeah, thought for being able to export clean logs. (P36)	18	11	6	5
	C5	Data Availability	...of having enough data available for the analysis . This also covers the problem of process steps being conducted outside of the system from which data is available.	I think missing data is one possible challenge. (P2)	11	9	6	3
	C6	Data Access	...due to missing permissions (legal, regulatory, organizational) to access the data .	Another one is also to check if we can get the data. Because we also already had cases where we couldn't get the data, it was not accessible, not for me and not for the data scientists. (P35)	8	6	5	1
	C7	Source System & Data Structure Knowledge	...during the data collection due to missing knowledge about the data structure and the source system from which data is extracted (e.g., relational databases).	So, process and system or data. They are most system than data missing knowledge I don't know why the system does it like it does and if there is a better way in the system, because I'm not an expert on the system and the settings there. (P9)	6	4	4	0

Phase	ID	Code	Description The code combines statements related to perceived challenges ...	Statement	Freq.	No.	#P	# A
Data Preprocessing	C8	Data Transformation	...during the preparation of a process mining compliant event log based on raw event data. It specifically covers adding attributes or activities to the event log and finding the correct level of aggregation depending on the case key.	I think the biggest challenge still is getting your data in a format that is ready to analyze. So typically, data comes from ERP systems like SAP or something like that. And it's not straightforward to put them in a process or in an event data or a XES format if you want. (P18)	33	17	9	8
	C9	Data Quality	...due to low data quality either in the final event log or already in the raw data .	Um, most problematic challenges are data quality issues. Frequent data quality issues also the mismatch of data recording and the business level reasoning, right. (P39)	27	15	6	9
	C10	Data Validation	...during checking data accuracy or the suitability of the available data to be analyzed with the help of process mining .	And for me my experience was that I use much um the most time I used in the process, in the whole process was to check if the data is ok and accurate. (P35)	8	5	3	2
Mining & Analysis	C11	Tool Knowledge	...associated with the use of a specific process mining tool . This covers a lack of familiarity with the tool or not having the tool used for a long time .	And they work all in a very similar way and they basically use the same algorithms. But, uh, remembering where those patterns are and how to click in the right sequence, it's not always easy for me. (P15)	28	18	8	10
	C12	Event Log & Data Model Understanding	...associated with the comprehension of the event log and the data model . Also, it covers missing insights about the data structure or problems caused by the absence of elements they are used to see in a data model.	I guess there are that there are a lot of tools for the preprocessing, but then the understanding ... getting acquainted with the log, I would say. (P10)	20	15	8	7
	C13	Process Mining Techniques	...related to missing or insufficient supported functionalities of specific process mining tools or in general including missing support for combining certain functions and methodologies .	And I think that that, as I said before, considering attributes further attributes within the process discovery, I think it's challenging, considering what I know about the methods that exist. (P4)	20	14	8	6
	C14	Access to Additional Information	...due to a lack of information or missing access of the process analysts to this information.	Sometimes there are information that are not provided by anyone, but the owners of the process are the domain experts who can explain better what went on there. Even in this case, let's say that basically the domain expertise was turned into a PDF document without that one, one could, you know, running circles very, very many times, but without knowing exactly where to look. (P8)	19	10	7	3
	C15	Process Visualization	...due to a misleading visualization of the event log in the form of a directly-follows graph (DFG) which can be found e.g., in the map (Disco) or in the variant explorer (Celonis).	So, there are many challenges one of them is process discovery. Ok, so the academic process, discovery algorithms are imprecise in a way that they generate lots of behavior that are not presented in the event logs. In Industry the visualization point, the notation that they use for visualizing process mining that is not accurate. (P29)	16	8	2	6

Phase	ID	Code	Description The code combines statements related to perceived challenges ...	Statement	Freq.	No.	#P	# A
Mining & Analysis	C16	Analysis Experience	...due to a subjective low level of prior experience as a process analyst .	They like one thing is for sure that the yeah, like the workforce needs to have someone experienced in it, like with the correct mindset and. Yeah, like , for example, Analysts' to get started with, and this is like a challenge if it's not available. (P24)	11	7	3	4
	C17	Analysis Focus	... of maintaining the big picture of the analysis despite the available details .	[...] once you have this, it's really the biggest challenge is not to lose yourself in the top-down analysis, OK? (P25)	7	6	6	0
Stakeholder evaluation	C18	Conclusions & Question Answering	... of answering the research questions and drawing conclusions based on the results of the process discovery.	After looking at the analysis for a while, they say, well, I don't really know where to find the answers. So, I am now a bit more familiar with the software. I don't really know what to do next. So, I don't know what to answer the the, where to find the answers to the the questions we give them. So, that is actually common a common theme I would say. (P20)	10	8	4	4
	C19	Recommendations & Next steps	...of formulating a concrete recommendation or deriving concrete next steps to foster the process improvement.	The issue is really what are you going to do with this? Ok, so what kind of exceptions or recommendations or proposals to change the process can you really do? (P25)	4	4	3	1

Overarching	C20	Process Domain Understanding	...due to a lack of/partial domain knowledge or unfamiliarity with domain-specific terminology used in the documentation or activity and attribute descriptions.	That I found challenging ... Yes, so perhaps not understanding the whole background, the whole rules, the whole process how we should work, and so not probably in process mining terminology, but in more like common terminology, that would have helped a little bit more. So, I was a bit confused on like, what's the difference between Sending the Fine, sending the notification and things like that. So that I found a challenge. (P20)	41	22	13	9
	C21	Collaboration with Stakeholders	...during the communication due to mismatching expectations, lack of understanding, different process perspectives and different backgrounds of the process analysts and the business and IT stakeholders.	I think one thing is to understand the costumer. To know what he wants and, as I said, to make that translation from business to IT and to make that bridge between business and IT. (P35)	24	15	9	6
	C22	Business Process Complexity	...due to the inherent complexity of business processes and the dependencies among them.	But my experience is that, that it's really easy to get tricked into believing that something is there, especially let's say in process mining you have the problem that you have this complex [process] behavior. (P12)	12	10	5	5
	C23	Enablement / Training	...due to a lack of available training opportunities or while conceptualizing trainings .	But I mean... I mean, just in terms of training, yeah, I mean, this is something... Training is probably the major aspect, I can think of that to enable what customers on the method, on the methodology, but also on the operational side. (P17)	15	9	6	3